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Research Article

**PSYCHOPHYSIOLOGICAL FEATURES OF STUDENTS
AEROBIC ABILITIES AND MAINTAINING A HEALTHY
LIFESTYLE****Ekaterina Y. Domrachyova, Oxana Y. Ilyakhina, Nikolay N. Severin, Igor N. Ozerov,
Larisa A. Kadutskaya**Belgorod Law Institute of Ministry of the Internal of the Russian Federation named after I.D.
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Katya260688@mail.ru**Article Received:** August 2020**Accepted:** September 2020**Published:** October 2020**Abstract:**

A healthy lifestyle has always been the basis of longevity and prosperity of citizens. However, today many people prefer to connect their lives with sports, while misinterpreting the concept of "healthy lifestyle". Citizens' health and sports medicine have always been a priority for the development of any state. After all, a healthy nation is a strong Foundation for creating a strong country. A healthy lifestyle at all stages of the formation of society was a priority in the activities of mankind. To do this, the country has the necessary material base, which is constantly being improved and distributed. Today, along with the old forms of physical training, a variety of sports clubs and sections are becoming increasingly popular. Their appearance contributes to the involvement of thousands of people in physical culture and sports. All this sets the Ministry of health and medical workers the task of constantly improving the organization and quality of medical support for physical culture and sports. Every year, the state holds various events and actions aimed at maintaining a "healthy spirit" among the population. So, the action, which has already become traditional and takes place in all regions of our country, is a symbol and promotion of a healthy lifestyle. From year to year, hundreds of thousands of people take part, thus showing how important it is in different age categories and being in different social situations to monitor their health.

Keywords: healthy lifestyle, aerobic capabilities, psychophysiological features, sports, occupation, sports medicine.

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INTRODUCTION:

The human body has been studied by scientists for several centuries. The psychophysiology of the human body is so unique and multifaceted, so it has not yet been possible to study all its aspects.

There are many areas of psychophysiology. But there is a psychophysiology that is really of great interest.

The psychophysiological state is an integral characteristic of a person's activity over a certain period of time, showing the uniqueness of the course of all processes depending on the reflected objects and phenomena of reality, the previous state and properties of the individual.

There is no unified concept of "healthy lifestyle" in the scientific literature. So, according to scientists in this field, a healthy lifestyle is a joint activity of a person and society aimed at maintaining and strengthening health. A number of authors believe that a healthy lifestyle is a set of personal and social practices for maintaining or achieving health, based on an interest in health, its value perception and goal setting, which stimulate its implementation in everyday life. However, not all citizens of the Russian Federation correctly interpret and understand the concept of "healthy lifestyle".

PURPOSE OF THE STUDY:

Recently, a new and fashionable trend among young people has appeared in our country, which is to visit fitness halls. At first glance, there is nothing dangerous about this activity, but on the contrary, it contributes to improving the health of the population. However, not everyone who visits such fitness centers knows about the correct exercise, proper nutrition system, work and rest regime. Often, when visiting sports complexes for the first time, young people immediately start working with complex projectiles, and also choose a working weight for themselves, which can even harm their health. Most often, after the first visits to gyms, "novice athletes" get various kinds of injuries, ranging from light sprains of ligaments, ending with partial or complete rupture of ligaments of various parts of the body. For young people who have decided to go in for sports and a healthy lifestyle for the first time, it is necessary to gradually prepare their body for physical activity, and it is best to seek help from qualified fitness trainers in order to prevent such situations.

It should be noted that training in fitness halls can contribute to the development of physical and spiritual health of a person, but only if a correct and

systematic approach to training is taken. In our opinion, the greatest harm to health is caused by bodybuilders. These athletes have an erroneous opinion about a healthy lifestyle. They often believe that many hours of training, the use of chemical supplements in the diet in order to stimulate the growth of muscle mass, helps to strengthen their physical health, but this is far from the case. As a result of their daily activities, the joints of the limbs begin to collapse under the influence of high loads, and the internal organs begin to lose their physiological functions due to the influence of chemical elements contained in biological additives.

Also, if we talk about such a category of the population as girls who also actively lead a healthy lifestyle, it should be noted that not all of them correctly approach the understanding of this term. Of course, at the first stages, leading a healthy lifestyle, a person tries to form the right diet of their food. On the Internet, there are quite a lot of different programs for beginners and professionals in this field, who choose their diet in accordance with personal criteria. However, not all young people are able to rationally limit themselves in various foods and meals.

In the twenty-first century, much attention has been paid to such a relatively new trend as "anorexia". Anorexia is a disease that is accompanied by a complete lack of appetite and a disorder of the entire body.

Young girls, leading a healthy lifestyle, proper nutrition and daily training destroy themselves and their body first of all, without realizing it. A large number of works have been devoted to scientists in the field of anorexia medicine, because, today, a large number of girls die, falling into the network of this disease. First of all, this is due to the fact that fighting for a beautiful body and the pursuit of popularity in social networks, people forget about health.

RESEARCH METHODS:

In institutes of physical culture, universities and faculties of physical culture, special attention is paid to the study of sports medicine. This is due to the fact that the physical education teacher and coach need medical knowledge to build and properly conduct the training process, physical education lessons and other sports events.

Sports medicine is a fairly young branch of medical science. It is defined as a separate specific area of clinical medicine, and its development contributes to the expansion of diagnostic methods in sports

medicine. This medical discipline studies health, physical development, morpho-functional features and functional reserves of the human body in connection with the impact of physical culture and sports on it. It is responsible for curative and preventive services, physical education, and for biomedical support of the training of athletes, which is an integral part of their sports training in General.

Sports medicine is designed to solve a number of specific problems that arise in the field of sports training. Organizations that are engaged in medical control over the training of athletes are United in the International Federation of sports medicine.

Sports medicine aims to solve a number of problems. These are constant monitoring of the health of people who are engaged in sports and physical culture both professionally and Amateur; regular diagnosis, treatment and prevention of injuries, diseases, and pathologies in athletes, and more.

One of the main tasks of this medical discipline is undoubtedly to achieve the health-improving effect of physical culture in people of different age categories, gender and health status. In addition, workers in this field of activity are required to constantly study and determine the optimal hygienic conditions for physical education, identify adverse effects on people during sports, and, if necessary, take measures to eliminate them as soon as possible. Also, sports medicine workers make decisions on nutrition and rehabilitation of people involved in sports who have suffered various diseases as a result of injuries. All of the above procedures can only be performed by a sports doctor. It is worth paying special attention to the procedure of medical examination of athletes, because it is carried out according to certain regulations. Thus, persons engaged in sports and physical culture are subject to a number of checks.

First, an initial medical examination is conducted, during which the doctor decides whether a person can be admitted to physical education. During such an examination, the medical professional conducts a number of instrumental studies of the patient, and ultimately makes a conclusion about whether to allow the person to play sports or suspend him. Then, after a certain period of time, during which the person is actively engaged in physical culture, the doctor conducts a second examination and determines what effect sports have on the health of the student. Athletes are subject to such medical examinations 1-2 times a year, in order to prevent diseases and injuries. In addition to the initial and repeated examinations,

there is also an additional medical examination. It is passed by those who have previously been engaged in sports, but have suffered various types of injuries, diseases or functional disorders and were forced to suspend physical education. During an additional examination, the sports doctor decides whether the athlete can be admitted to training, or about his further rehabilitation. the

Physical training of students is directly related to the aerobic capabilities of the body. When performing long-term continuous exercises: running, skiing, swimming, sports walking, aerobic capabilities of a person are effectively formed.

Aerobic performance refers to the ability of the human body to perform work using oxygen absorbed during work to restore it.

Aerobic loads can lead the body to perform three tasks: 1) the highest degree of oxygen consumption increases; 2) the ability to maintain this state for a long time develops; 3) the speed of respiratory actions increases to the maximum value.

Cyclical sports, namely: running, walking, swimming, biathlon, cross - country skiing are means of increasing respiratory endurance, which achieve the highest respiratory and cardiac load, as well as maintain a high concentration of oxygen in the blood for a long period of time. The development of non-standard thinking is developed with the help of training observation.

There is no perfection in the development of observation, so it must be developed, because it, along with hearing and vision, is a psychophysiological indicator of information perception.

Observation is developed by different methods. One of the techniques is to memorize items laid out on the table. Usually lay out various items different from others. The student looks at the items for a certain amount of time, then the table is covered with a cloth and the student names everything that he remembered, but at the same time he must name not only the item, but also describe it. This technique will be carried out until the student accurately and clearly describes all the subjects, and the subjects change every time.

After the student has learned to remember the type and position of objects laid out on the table, they begin to train in nature. Training in nature takes place

as follows: the student looks at a distance of 100 meters, remembers the situation, and then turns away. The assistant changes the state of the existing landscape at this time. turning back, the student names the existing changes. Each time the distance increases and reaches 300 m. It is at this distance that the trained student should detect changes: crumpled grass, broken branches, cigarette smoke, and other changes.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

Classes with students, if possible, should be arranged in natural conditions of the area, in places rich in oxygen (forest, river). It is recommended to perform the exercises with an intensity close to critical.

The duration of operation at the maximum oxygen consumption level does not exceed 10 – 12 minutes. Only qualified cadets maintain the intensity of physical activity, which is close to critical for 1 – 1.5 hours. Subsequently, discoordination begins in the cardiovascular and respiratory systems, oxygen consumption decreases, and the effectiveness of the load decreases.

The most effective way to develop aerobic capabilities is anaerobic work, which is performed in the form of short-term simple repetitions at certain time intervals of rest. This method is called the method of repeated and variable interval exercise.

In the ratio of work and rest, a certain period of equilibrium occurs, which is distributed between the body's oxygen reserve and a certain rate of oxygen consumption. Due to this, secondary work can last for a certain period of time.

During repeated physical work, the amount of oxygen consumption varies all the time: from increasing to decreasing.

Aerobic capabilities are inseparable from the correct setting of the respiratory system. External (pulmonary) respiration is not considered a primary condition that limits the aerobic capabilities of the body, it plays an important role for the endurance of an athlete-cadet. Setting breathing is the main health - improving tasks of physical education of a cadet.

Monitoring the heart rate range is a modern word of technology in cardio exercises. Physical activity can be divided into five zones, according to the percentage values of the maximum heart rate (HR) of cadet athletes. These heart rate zones allow you to freely monitor the intensity of the training process.

Training in the 1st range is characterized by low intensity in work. The main principle: physical performance increases not only during training, but also during the recovery process. This training, which has the lowest working intensity, is indispensable in the recovery period of sports.

Training in the 2nd range is characterized by increased endurance, being an organic part of any training program. In this range, simple aerobic exercises are performed. Long-term training in this range guarantees productive energy consumption. To achieve certain results, you need a certain regularity, perseverance and perseverance.

Aerobic endurance becomes higher during the training process in the heart rate range 3. the Intensity of training in this range is much higher than in the first two ranges, but it remains aerobic. The training process in this range consists of certain intervals that alternate with recovery periods. Training in this range is well suited for improving blood circulation in the athlete's heart, as well as in skeletal muscles.

If the goal of the cadet is to perform the training process to the limit of their capabilities, then they simply need training in ranges 4 and 5, in which anaerobic training is performed at intervals of up to 10 minutes. The shorter the interval, the higher the intensity. It is necessary that between the intervals in the training process in the ranges there is enough time for the recovery process of the body. The structure of training processes in 4 and 5 ranges is intended for the implementation of indicators of the maximum value.

A cadet-athlete can set individual settings for heart rate ranges based on laboratory indicators of maximum heart rate (HRmax), or independently make these measurements during measurements in practice. When training in certain heart rate ranges, you need to use it to the full. It is good if the cadet-athlete manages to keep the heart rate values in the average range cycle. Your heart rate adapts over time to the intensity of a particular workout. For example, when switching from the first range to the third range, the body's blood circulation and heart rate adapt within 3-5 minutes.

The rate of heart rate adjustment to the intensity of the training process directly depends on certain factors: environmental factors, the physical condition of the person, the level of recovery. You need to pay attention to your own physiological feelings of

fatigue and try to adapt your own training program to your feelings.

Special physical indicators can be achieved by athletes training in the middle mountains of Russia. The main feature of training cadets who are part of the Institute's track and field team in mountainous areas is the lack of oxygen. Hypoxia develops the body's endurance under the usual loads. In addition, training in the mountains is held before various competitions, for example, in Kislovodsk, as well as for rehabilitation and recovery of lost strength.

CONCLUSION:

Thus, long-distance runners and cross-country skiers have the greatest aerobic capabilities, and swimmers and cyclists are slightly inferior to them. Attention is drawn to the fact that aerobic performance in sports walking is very slightly inferior to runners and practically does not differ from the data of swimmers. Thus, all types of cyclic exercises lead to a marked increase in the body's ability to absorb (consume) oxygen, and sports walking in this respect is almost as good as more "fast" types of aerobic exercise. Students can practice sports walking, swimming, and Cycling in their free time.

In our opinion, in order to start practicing, monitor your health and adhere to a healthy lifestyle, you do not need to exhaust your body with diets, various foods that contain substances that negatively affect human health in General. First of all, an important criterion for a healthy lifestyle is a proper balanced diet, which will be aimed at enriching the body with vitamins. To do this, you do not need to use chemical additives that will negatively affect the human body and the brain in the first place. It is enough to review your diet and make changes in the form of adding various products with a predominance of vitamins of group A and B. Also, physical training is an integral part of normal human life. In accordance with the order of the Minister of defense of the Russian Federation of 21.04.2009 No. 200 "On approval Of the manual on physical training in The armed Forces of the Russian Federation", physical training contributes to:

- first, increasing the body's resistance to adverse environmental factors;
- secondly, the education of mental stability and moral and strong-willed qualities;
- third, the formation of readiness to endure extreme physical and mental stress.

Also, a lot of important factors that affect human health is charging. You need to start your morning

every day with a five-minute charge, which will help to Wake up the body and set up the body's muscles to work for the whole day. It is not necessary to go to the fitness room and spend two or more hours on training, it is enough just to pay more attention to your body also in the form of walking in the fresh air, swimming in the pool, which puts a load on all muscle groups.

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